

Notes on the crab spider *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* Millot, 1942 in South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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Abstract: The crab spider *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* Millot, 1942 has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In South Africa the species was regularly sampled from agroecosystems and is recognised as one of five agrobionts that play an important role as natural control agents of pest species. The general morphology of both sexes of the species is discussed, with photographs of live specimens and notes on their behaviour, biology, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa.

Key words: agroecosystems, agrobiont, behaviour, biodiversity, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) large numbers of Thomisidae were sampled and presently 143 species from 37 genera are recorded from South Africa.

The genus *Misumenops* F.O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1900 contains 55 species and subspecies (World Spider Catalog, 2023). Some of these species were formerly listed in the genera *Diaea*, *Misumena*, and *Synema*. *Misumenops* is sometimes regarded as a genus of convenience, intermediate between *Misumena* and *Diaea*. Gertsch (1939), however, considered *Misumenops* as being representative of a group of spiders quite different from related genera.

All the aforementioned genera are listed under Misumenini from the diagnoses provided by Simon (1895) and Mello-Leitão (1929), which are chiefly based on the eye pattern and some other somatic characters. The minor differences between them are difficult to observe and therefore the identification and generic placement of the species have been confusing at best.

A study of Palearctic, Oriental, and some African, Pacific, and American species (Lehtinen, 1993; 2004) revealed that the majority of species assigned to *Misumenops* are not related to the type species and belong elsewhere. Considering the lack of proper drawings of the type species and principles applied to the taxonomy of the Misumenini, it is not surprising that the concept of *Misumenops* is quite vague. Lehtinen and Marusik (2008) redefine *Misumenops* and numerous New World species were moved to other genera.

Misumenops is not well represented in the Afrotropical region and only two species have been recorded to date, of which one was formerly placed in the genus *Misumena*. Lessert (1919) regarded *Misumenops* as a subgenus of *Misumena* as they resemble *Misumena* in shape and colour but differ in having many erect setae on the body and legs (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983).

In this paper, we provide more information on the crab spider that we presently recognise as *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* Millot, 1942. It is an African endemic described from Guinea and reported from several countries throughout Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2023). This paper aims to collate all information on the species, including the morphology of both sexes based on live specimens, their behaviour, biology, distribution, and conservation status, with notes on their presence in crops and agrobiont status. The data were gathered during SANSA surveys.

Figures 1–2. *Misumenops rubrodecoratus*. 1. Female lateral view. 2. Female dorsal view. 3. Male anterior view. Photo credits: 1. Vida vd Walt. 2–3. Peter Webb.

Figures 4–9. *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* female showing the colour variations. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

TAXONOMY

Misumenops rubrodecoratus Millot, 1942

Misumenops rubrodecorata Millot, 1942: 37; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 51.

Misumenops rubrodecoratus Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2020: 51, 52.

Description: Size: TL females 4.4–6.7 mm. Female: yellow to pale green (green fades in alcohol to yellow), sometimes with red or brown patterns or lines on carapace and abdomen; legs I and II sometimes banded with red or brown (Figs 4–9). Carapace as wide as long, low and slightly convex; surface clothed with numerous erect spiniform setae (Fig. 2); clypeus vertical, with four pairs of long primary setae on margin. Eyes in two recurved rows; lateral eyes larger than median eyes, situated on conjoined tubercles (Fig. 1). Sternum heart-shaped. Abdomen round in dorsal view; flattened, clothed with numerous erect spiniform setae. Legs: anterior two pairs approximately equal in length and thickness, longer and stronger than posterior pairs; pro-lateral surface of femora I and II with strong setae; ventral surface of tibiae and metatarsi with double row of macrosetae. Epigyne shown in Figs 10–11.

Male (Figs 3 & 13–14). Size: males 1.5–4.0 mm. Male differs structurally from the female as follows: setae on body, especially those on abdomen, longer and more numerous; legs longer and thinner, macro-setae on tibiae and metatarsi I and II weakly developed. Male palp shown in Fig. 12.

Figures 10–14. *Misumenops rubrodecoratus*. 10–11. Female genitalia. 12. Male palp. 13–14. Male habitus. Photo credits: 10–12. After Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983). 13–14. Peter Webb.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

The species was described by Millot (1942) from Kindia, Guinea. During a revision by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983), specimens from different museums were studied and new records from Mali, Namibia, South Africa, Sudan, Upper Volta, and Zimbabwe were recorded.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

The species is widely distributed throughout South Africa (Map 1). Detailed locality data with coordinates can be found in Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020 (pp. 51–52).

Map 1. Known distribution of *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* Millot, 1942.

LIFESTYLE

Misumenops rubrodecoratus is a very common thomisid species recorded from South Africa. Adults are collected throughout the year, except in the winter months. They are active during the day and prey on a variety of small invertebrates, potentially playing an important role in the natural control of pests such as aphids, red spider mites, and thrips. They inhabit grass, shrubs, flowers, and trees, and have been sampled from all the floral biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

It was one of the 44 thomisid species sampled from crops in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013), and sampled from avocado, citrus, cotton, kenaf, lucerne, macadamia, maize, pecans, pine plantations, pistachio, pumpkin, sugar cane, sunflower, strawberries, and tomatoes.

In citrus orchards, of the 18 crab spider species collected, *M. rubrodecoratus* was the most abundant. Van den Berg *et al.* (1992) observed that they prey on adult citrus psylla. Feeding experiments indicated that they also prey on aphids, red spider mites, and thrips.

In cotton fields, *M. rubrodecoratus* was the most abundant species collected in five cotton-growing areas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999). On cotton, the species is mostly found on leaves and stems, near bracts of cotton plants, as well as hiding under dry leaves on the ground (Van den Berg, 1989). In the laboratory they preyed on red spider mites, the first two larval stages of *Helicoverpa armigera*, as well as on aphids (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999).

Of the arboreal spiders collected over a 12-month period from three macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa, *M. rubrodecoratus* was the most abundant thomisid species sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001).

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